

Minute-Scale High-Temperature Synthesis of Polymeric Carbon Nitride Photoanodes

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Polymeric carbon nitride (CN) has emerged as a promising photoanodic material in water-splitting photoelectrochemical cells (PEC). However, the current deposition methods of CN layers on substrates usually include a long heating process at 500–550 °C, which might cause sublimation or decomposition of the CN monomers and destruction of the substrate, leading to a nonuniform CN film. Herein, a simple, fast, and scalable energy-economic procedure to synthesize homogenous CN films is introduced. The predesigned CN monomers film is subjected for several minutes to higher temperatures than the standard calcination procedure. The short heating process allows the formation of a uniform CN layer, with excellent contact with the substrate and good activity as a photoanode in PEC. The optimal CN photoanode reaches photocurrent densities of $\approx 200 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 versus reversible hydrogen electrode in neutral and acidic solutions and $120 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in a basic solution.

photocorrosion under operational conditions.^[2,8] Metal (oxy)nitrides are prone to self-oxidative deactivation in oxygen-rich atmospheres, which is common in PEC water-splitting.^[8,10] Since the first report of photocatalytic water-splitting using CN in 2009,^[11] and the first report of CN photoelectrodes that was presented by Zhang et al. in 2010,^[12] reaching less than $1 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, great progress has been achieved—driven by the chemical and thermal stability of CN on the one hand and its low cost, ease of scalable synthesis, and benign nature, on the other hand. Unlike CN powder, which is used as a dispersed photocatalyst, at for applications such as photoelectrochemical cells, light-emitting diodes, and solar cells, the deposition of the CN on a conductive substrate is

1. Introduction

Polymeric carbon nitride (CN) materials have emerged as metal-free, low-cost, and environmentally friendly semiconductors in various applications, including photoelectrodes in photoelectrochemical water-splitting.^[1–7] Most of the research on photoelectrodes in the photoelectrochemical water-splitting field has focused on metal oxides, metal chalcogenides, and metal (oxy) nitrides; each has advantages and drawbacks.^[6,8] Metal oxides, such as TiO_2 and WO_3 , are easy to prepare and are chemically stable under photoelectrochemical cells (PEC) conditions, but they suffer from a wide bandgap, which allows them to absorb only a small fraction of the solar spectrum.^[8,9] Metal chalcogenides, conversely, have better light absorption but suffer from

required. The deposition of CN layers on different substrates can be divided into two main categories: 1) ex situ deposition of prepared CN powder and 2) in situ growth of a CN layer directly on the substrate. Due to the bulky nature of the CN materials, ex situ deposition leads to a loosened contact with the substrate, and usually, a binder is needed.^[4,6] Therefore, most of the research is concentrated on the direct growth of CN, starting with the deposition of CN monomers on the substrate or by physical deposition methods.

Generally, the in situ methods comprise two steps:^[4–6] the first one is the deposition or growth of nitrogen-rich monomers (such as melamine, urea, thiourea, dicyanamide, etc.), forming a film of the monomers on the substrate. The following step is the calcination process, in which these monomers polymerize, forming the final CN electrode. Most in situ preparation techniques (solvo-thermal strategy,^[13] direct growth,^[14] microcontact-printing,^[15] thermal vapor condensation,^[16,17] spray-coating,^[18] etc.) differ in the deposition or growth method of the monomers' film but maintain a similar "standard" calcination process of slowly heating this film to 500–550 °C and keeping the final temperature for several hours, usually under inert atmosphere (Table S1, Supporting Information). A major drawback of a long heating process is the possible sublimation and decomposition of the CN monomers and final layer, which may lead to a less uniform film.^[19,20] In addition, from an economical point of view, a long calcination process at a high temperature consumes much energy. Therefore, finding a straightforward, short, and scalable method for reproducible preparation of CN layers with intimate contact with the substrate is of utmost importance. Fast-heating

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pyrolysis has recently been used to synthesize carbon and carbon nitride materials.^[21–24] This method entails the introduction of the starting monomers to an elevated temperature (higher than the traditional one) for a short time. The high temperature enables fast condensation of the monomers, and negligible degradation is obtained thanks to the short time at and about the target temperature. Moreover, it allows using substrates which are not stable at these high temperatures (e.g., glass).

Here, we report the facile, scalable, energy-saving, and reproducible synthesis of CN layers on conductive substrates using a fast heating method. We introduce the monomer films into a preheated tube oven at 650–680 °C for 5–20 min under a low-oxygen atmosphere. As a result, homogenous CN films with good contact with the conductive substrate are obtained. We studied the role of the starting monomers on the final CN film properties and quality in detail. We found that utilizing the supramolecular assembly of melem–melamine (Mel–M) leads to the most active films due to the high thermal stability and low sublimation of melem, while melamine contributes to the intimate contact of the film with the conductive substrate.^[25] The optimized films serve as photoanodes and exhibit high photocurrent densities with a low overpotential in water-splitting PEC.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Preparation and Characterization of Mel–M Supramolecular Assemblies

For an efficient fast heating synthesis of CN films, we have used a three-step approach: (i) design of supramolecular assemblies that should allow thermal polymerization into a three-dimensional network of a carbon nitride polymer; (ii) preparing a

supramolecular paste based on the supramolecular assemblies and using a doctor-blade technique for its deposition over transparent conductive oxide substrates (in this case, fluorine-doped tin-oxide coated glass, referred to henceforth as FTO); and (iii) fast heating of the substrates with the precursor film at elevated temperatures for short time intervals, resulting in homogenous photoactive CN electrodes (**Scheme 1**).

Mel–M supramolecular assemblies were synthesized following the procedure described by Xia et al.^[25] (detailed in the Experimental Section). First, melem was synthesized by thermal polymerization of melamine at 400 °C for 12 h in an air furnace. Next, three types of supramolecular assemblies were prepared, consisting of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1 molar ratios of melem:melamine and labeled as MelM, 2MelM, and 3MelM, respectively. These supramolecular assemblies serve as the optimal precursors for the fast synthesis of CN films at a high temperature due to the individual benefits of each component. Melem endows thermal stability,^[26] while good contact with the FTO forms thanks to the melamine.^[25] Thermogravimetric analysis measurements of melem, melamine, and the three supramolecular assemblies under a nitrogen environment confirm the improved thermal stability of Mel–M with higher melem content (Figure S1, Supporting Information).

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the supramolecular assemblies and their components reveal a pronounced diffraction signal at $2\theta = 10.9^\circ$, confirming the formation of a crystalline structure, as was shown previously by our group (Figure 1a).^[25] The Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) measurements further confirm the formation of the supramolecular assemblies as the two sharp peaks in the 3400–3500 cm^{-1} region in melamine and melem, corresponding to N–H vibrations, diminish in the assemblies following the aggregation via hydrogen bonds.

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the FTO/CN preparation route. Two FTO substrates coated with a Mel–M supramolecular assembly films (after doctor-blading a Mel–M dispersion in ethylene glycol, followed by drying) are placed facing each other, with an additional 0.10 g of melem between them and wrapped in aluminum foil, in a “sandwich”-like manner. Then, the “sandwiches” are inserted into a preheated tube furnace for 5, 10, or 20 min, at 650 or 680 °C, while maintaining a nitrogen flow. After cooling down to room temperature and removing excess CN powder, two CN films over FTO are obtained.

Figure 1. a) XRD patterns and b) FTIR spectra of melamine, melem, and the supramolecular assemblies: MelM, 2MelM, and 3MelM. c,d) Top-view SEM images of 3MelM film at different magnifications.

In addition, there are notable differences between the melamine spectrum, and the melem and the assemblies' spectra at $1000\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which arise from their different structure: triazine ring in melamine compared to a heptazine ring in melem and its species (Figure 1b).^[27,28]

The supramolecular assemblies are dispersed in ethylene glycol and doctor-bladed over a clean FTO substrate.^[5] Top-view scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of 3MelM film reveal a uniform coating of the FTO, with a square-like morphology (Figure 1c,d). Cross-sectional SEM images disclose good contact of the film with the substrate, and an estimated thickness of $\approx 27\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (Figure S2, Supporting Information). Increasing the molar ratio to 4:1 Mel–M resulted in poor contact with the FTO due to excess of melem, as 3:1 Mel–M molar ratio is ideal for full hydrogen bonding in the supramolecular assembly.^[25] Therefore, it cracks and partially peels off during the preparation process (i.e., during the drying of the supramolecular assembly paste) and cannot be used for CN synthesis (Figure S3, Supporting Information).

2.2. Preparation and Characterization of CN Films

To transform the supramolecular precursor films into well-attached FTO/CN, two FTO pieces are placed facing each other with 0.1 g melem powder between them in a “sandwich”-like manner, as depicted in Scheme 1. Each “sandwich” is inserted into a preheated tube furnace for 5–20 min at 650 or 680 °C, under a nitrogen atmosphere. After cooling down through natural convection, the “sandwich” is separated, and excess CN powder (product of melem thermal polymerization) is removed.

These CN layers over FTO are labeled as Precursor_{T/t}, where T = calcination temperature (°C) and t = calcination duration (min). Since the electrodes prepared from 3MelM films (3MelM_{T/t}) showed the best photoelectrochemical activity (as will be shown later), we focus on them for further investigation.

The XRD patterns of 3MelM_{650/10} and 3MelM_{650/20} reveal an incomplete polymerization of the supramolecular precursor into a typical polymeric carbon nitride (i.e., based on repeating heptazine units, such as melon),^[29,30] a typical CN interplanar stacking diffraction appears at 27.6° , while the typical CN in-plane diffraction at $\approx 13^\circ$ is still missing.^[31,32] To shorten the calcination process, we increased the temperature of the oven to 680 °C. This temperature was selected due to two technical reasons that had to be taken into consideration: the durability of the FTO and its conductivity at a very high temperature,^[33] and the melting point of the aluminum foil ($\approx 660^\circ\text{C}$) enclosing the “sandwich.”^[34] Since the calcination process lasts 5–20 min, these two factors did not affect the synthesis process. At 680 °C, 5 min was not enough for complete polymerization, as can be detected from the XRD pattern of 3MelM_{680/5}, which exhibits three peaks that correspond to 3MelM at 11.0° , 12.2° , and 27.9° , while 3MelM_{680/10} and 3MelM_{680/20} show the two typical CN diffraction peaks detailed above (Figure 2a).^[31,32]

The FTIR spectra further support the incomplete polymerization claim, as N–H vibration peaks, which result from incomplete polymerization, are evident in 3MelM_{650/10} and 3MelM_{680/5} at around $3400\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and are also noticeable in 3MelM_{650/20}. Additional differences are present in the $1000\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region of C–N heterocycles stretching modes, as 3MelM_{650/10} and 3MelM_{680/5} spectra exhibit similarities to the 3MelM spectrum (Figure 2b). C 1s X-ray photoelectron

Figure 2. a) XRD patterns, b) FTIR spectra, c) C 1s, and d) N 1s XPS spectra of the FTO/CN films: 3MeIM_{650/10}, 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/5}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20}. All patterns and spectra are vertically offset for clarity.

spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of all films can be deconvoluted into three peaks: C=C, C-NH₂, and N=C-N, centered at 284.8, 286.2 eV, and in the range of 288.1–288.4 eV, respectively.^[35,36] The significant variations in the location of the latter peak stem from different chemical environments. In addition, surface oxidation of 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20} films is evident by the appearance of C=O peaks, which are mostly pronounced in the 3MeIM_{680/20} film.^[37–40] Moreover, in 3MeIM_{680/20}, an additional peak at 290.8 eV, attributed to C—O bonds (Figure 2c) is also present.^[41] N 1s XPS spectra of all films are deconvoluted into three peaks: C=N—C, N-(C)₃, and N—H, located at 398.7–399.3, 399.8–400.4, and 401.0–401.6 eV, respectively.^[35,42–44] In accordance with the C 1s spectra, the variations in the center of the deconvoluted N 1s peaks stem from different chemical environments. Moreover, an additional N—O signal at 402.3–402.6 eV in the 3MeIM_{680/10} and 3MeIM_{680/20} spectra indicates extensive oxidation at the films' surface (Figure 2d).^[45,46] Elemental analysis (EA) suggests a slight increase in carbon quantity of 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20} compared to 3MeIM_{650/10} and 3MeIM_{680/5}. The amount of oxygen is comparable in all films (10–11 at%), while in 3MeIM_{680/5} it is the lowest (about 8.8 at%), probably due to its short calcination time (Table S2, Supporting Information).

From these results, alongside the C 1s and N 1s XPS spectra, we conclude that most of the oxidation happens on the surface of the films and not in the bulk due to residual oxygen available during the thermal process, since the system is partially open to air to allow insertion and removal of the samples despite maintaining a constant high nitrogen flow from one side of the tube (as was illustrated in Scheme 1).

The films' UV–vis diffuse reflectance spectra (Figure S4, Supporting Information) exhibit improved absorption for 3MeIM_{680/20}. Moreover, a noticeable red shift manifests in narrower calculated optical bandgaps (E_g) from a Tauc plot analysis assuming a direct E_g (Figure 3a).^[47] 3MeIM_{680/20} has the narrowest E_g of 2.83 eV, while 3MeIM_{650/20} and 3MeIM_{680/10} have similar $E_g = 2.86$ eV. 3MeIM_{650/10} and 3MeIM_{680/5} have the widest bandgaps, of 2.89 eV and 2.90 eV, respectively. These results correspond to the physical appearance of the electrodes; 3MeIM_{650/10} and 3MeIM_{680/5} have a pale yellowish shade, while 3MeIM_{650/20} and 3MeIM_{680/10} exhibit a stronger shade of yellow. 3MeIM_{680/20} has a strong yellow color typical to CN materials (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Figure 3b presents an energy diagram of the films based on the calculated E_g values and valence band (VB) positions, collected from XPS-VB measurements (Figure S6, Supporting Information).^[48]

Figure 3. a) Tauc plot analysis for the determination of the optical bandgaps of the CN films. b) Proposed energy bands diagram of the CN films on the NHE scale. c) PL spectra of the CN films; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 380$ nm. d) Top-view SEM image of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ (insets: the corresponding digital photo and cross-sectional SEM image).

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra (excited at 380 nm) suggest a possible improved charge separation in $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$ —the most polymerized material—while $3\text{MeIM}_{680/5}$, the least polymerized material, exhibits the highest PL intensity, indicating the highest electron–hole recombination rate (Figure 3c).^[49]

The top-view SEM image of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ reveals a full, homogeneous coverage of the FTO (Figure 3d). High-magnification images reveal the morphology of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, which consists of ≈ 1.5 μm pores in the microstructure (Figure S7, Supporting Information). The cross-sectional image indicates that the film consists of a layered structure, most probably because of the introduction of melem powder during the calcination process. The bottom part, which is closer to the FTO, is dense, while the upper part is more capacious. Overall, the film has a uniform thickness of ≈ 17 μm (Figure 3d, inset).

Since the only size limitation in the fast heating synthesis method is the diameter of the tube furnace, large-scale electrodes can be produced. Figure S8, Supporting Information shows 40.8 cm^2 (6.8 $\text{cm} \times 6.0$ cm) $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ and 50.0 cm^2 (10.0 $\text{cm} \times 5.0$ cm) $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$ electrodes. Furthermore, an adhesion test, performed by placing a heavy object on top of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ covered by scotch tape for two hours, reveals excellent mechanical stability, as the electrode remained almost intact (Figure S9, Supporting Information).^[18]

2.3. PEC Performance of the CN Photoanodes

The CN photoanodes were electrochemically characterized during operation in a water-splitting scenario in a standard three-electrode closed cell, using a 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution as the electrolyte under 1-sun back- and front-side illumination, unless stated otherwise. Chronoamperometry measurements were conducted at 1.23 V versus (vs) reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE). First, different CN films, prepared from supramolecular assemblies of varying molar ratios and calcined at 680 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min, namely, $\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, $2\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, and $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ were measured (Figure S10, Supporting Information). $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ exhibited the highest photocurrent density, therefore we decided to focus on the 3MeIM electrodes.

To evaluate the photoanodic performance, only the well-polymerized CN films are compared: $3\text{MeIM}_{650/20}$, $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, and $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$. At the described alkaline conditions, all electrodes show good photocurrent stability for 10 min, with $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ giving the highest photocurrent density of ≈ 120 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 4a and Figure S11a–c, Supporting Information). In a photoanodic PEC configuration, the photogenerated holes oxidize water or a hole scavenger at the CN surface while electrons migrate to the FTO. In all the CN electrodes, better activity is achieved under back-side illumination, because of

Figure 4. Photoelectrochemical characterization of 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20} films as photoanodes. Chronoamperometric measurements (photocurrent density at 1.23 V vs RHE) under cycling 1-sun on/off illumination: a) in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution and b) in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution containing 10% v/v TEOA as a hole scavenger. c) LSV curves of the CN electrodes in 0.1 M KOH; dashed lines—in the dark; complete lines—under illumination. d) IPCE plots of 3MeIM_{680/10} at 1.23 V versus RHE in 0.1 M KOH and in 0.1 M KOH containing 10% v/v TEOA (hole scavenger).

the shorter distance the photogenerated electrons need to travel to reach the FTO.^[50] Since water oxidation is kinetically hindered over CN photoanodes, we added triethanolamine (TEOA) as a hole scavenger to the electrolyte to reduce the recombination of electron–hole pairs. This improved the photocurrent density of all electrodes, with 3MeIM_{650/20} and 3MeIM_{680/10} reaching $\approx 190 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 4b). It is worth noting that in the presence of TEOA, 3MeIM_{680/10} exhibits impressive photocurrent stability of about $100 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ even after 20 h of constant illumination (Figure S12, Supporting Information), opening the possibility for hydrogen production at the cathode while oxidizing an organic molecule over the photoanode. In addition, 3MeIM_{680/10} produces highly repeatable results, as the difference in photocurrent density between three sets of chronoamperometry measurements reaches 15% at most, both in front-side and back-side illumination (Figure S13, Supporting Information).

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements without a hole scavenger show a typical CN behavior; no noticeable current is measured in the dark until 1.5–1.7 V, where the sharp increase in current stems from electrochemical water oxidation. All electrodes display a monotonous photocurrent increase with increased applied potential, while the lowest onset potential, of 0.25 V, belongs to 3MeIM_{680/10} (Figure 4c). Comparing the

measured photocurrents in the presence and absence of a hole scavenger allows the estimation of a charge transfer efficiency of 3MeIM_{680/10} photoanodes, which reaches up to 52% at 0.7 V versus RHE (Figure S14, Supporting Information). In addition, this electrode obtained incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) values of $\approx 4\%$ and $\approx 6\%$ at short wavelengths, in the absence and in the presence of TEOA, respectively (Figure 4d).

Additional chronoamperometry measurements were performed in neutral (phosphate buffer, pH 6.67) and acidic (0.5 M H₂SO₄, pH 0.46) conditions. In both cases, similar trends are observed: 3MeIM_{680/10}, 3MeIM_{650/20}, and 3MeIM_{680/20} reach photocurrent density values of ≈ 200 , 150, and $50 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$, respectively (Figure S15a,b, Supporting Information). Furthermore, 3MeIM_{680/10} demonstrates the best activity in a neutral solution, as the photocurrent density remained quite stable for one hour of continuous illumination following an initial decrease to $30 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ over the first 30 min (Figure S16, Supporting Information). In the absence of a hole scavenger, there is an enhanced recombination of electron–hole pairs and self-oxidation of the CN by the generated holes, which leads to deterioration in the activity of the CN electrodes.^[5] The increased oxygen content of 3MeIM_{680/10} following a 30 min

chronoamperometry measurement in 0.1 M KOH (Table S3, Supporting Information) supports this degradation mechanism. Since the CN film itself gets oxidized, it cannot continue to oxidize the electrolyte to the same extent as at the beginning of the measurement, and therefore its activity deteriorates.

We conducted chronoamperometry measurements of three other CN electrodes to test their performance compared to the proposed method: the first one is prepared from the 3MeIM supramolecular film, using a ‘standard’ calcination process of 550 °C for four hours (denoted as 3MeIM_{550/4h}). This electrode demonstrates lower PEC activity than the fast heating procedure, with a photocurrent density of only $\approx 30 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V versus RHE. Another set of reference electrodes was prepared without melem powder between the 3MeIM films during synthesis. These electrodes show poor activity, as their photocurrent drops drastically during the 10-minute measurement. The last one is 3MeIM_{680/10}, which was prepared with two layers of scotch tape during the doctor blade process instead of one like all other films, to evaluate the influence of the film thickness on the performance (this film is denoted 3MeIM_{680/10} 2 L). In this case, the photocurrent density is also lower than the one-layer 3MeIM_{680/10} (Figure S17a–c, Supporting Information). It is important to mention that during the doctor blade procedure with two layers of scotch tape, some of the films peeled off, as seen in Figure S18, Supporting Information. This phenomenon indicates poor contact of 3MeIM_{680/10} 2 L with the FTO substrate, which is probably the reason behind its poor activity. 3MeIM_{680/10} also has improved charge separation compared to the CN reference electrodes, while 3MeIM_{680/10} 2 L has the highest electron–hole recombination rate (Figure S19, Supporting Information).

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements suggest highly improved charge transfer efficiency of 3MeIM_{680/10} and 3MeIM_{550/4h} compared to 3MeIM_{680/10} 2 L, 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/20}, and 3MeIM_{680/10} that was prepared without melem powder and exhibits poor efficiency (Figure S20, Supporting Information).

Figure S21a, Supporting Information, shows the experimental value of evolved oxygen gas over 3MeIM_{680/10} compared to the theoretical value (calculated from the chronoamperometry measurement presented in Figure S18b, Supporting Information). The corresponding Faradaic efficiency value is 35.6% after 33 min. This value is considered relatively good for a cocatalyst-free CN photoanode yet demonstrates the parasitic oxidation reactions taking place at the photoanode. Evolved hydrogen gas was also measured, reaching $0.181 \mu\text{mol cm}^{-2}$ after 20 min (Figure S22, Supporting Information).

Characterization of the photoanodes after the operation (post-PEC) discloses a significant change in the morphology of the electrode (SEM images of 3MeIM_{680/10}; Figure S23, Supporting Information). Following the 20 h long stability test, two distinct layers are detected: a compact layer attached to the FTO, with a uniform thickness of $\approx 15 \mu\text{m}$, and another sporadic layer on top of the aforementioned one, which appears only on some parts of the electrode’s surface.

We believe that the difference between the performance of the electrodes arises not only from the intrinsic properties of the CN layers but also from the increasing FTO substrate resistance due to thermal treatment. Measured at a fixed distance of 1 cm, the

resistance of blank FTO before synthesis is 25.4Ω , while the resistances of blank FTO substrates calcined at similar conditions to 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20} are 28.7, 27.5, and 30.1Ω , respectively. The latter resistance value contributes to the moderate activity of 3MeIM_{680/20} photoanode despite the CN’s higher degree of polymerization and lower optical bandgap. In addition, the resistance of a blank FTO substrate calcined according to the standard calcination process of 550 °C for 4 hours (similarly to 3MeIM_{550/4h}) is 28.8Ω , proving that our new synthesis method is harmless to the FTO substrate due to its short duration, despite reaching very high temperatures, which usually harms conductive substrates as FTO.

3. Conclusion

To conclude, we demonstrate a fast, simple, scalable, reproducible, and straightforward method to grow a homogenous CN layer on a conductive substrate. To do so, we use fast calcination of the designed supramolecular precursors layer on a conductive substrate at temperatures beyond the typical calcination temperature of CN. The fast calcination enables the fabrication of a homogenous CN layer with excellent contact with the conductive layer. Notably, the conductivity of the conductive layer remained almost unchanged compared to the traditional calcination process. The resulting CN electrodes exhibit state-of-the-art performance as photoanodes in water-splitting PEC, with good activity over a wide pH range ($120 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in alkaline electrolyte and $200 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ in neutral and acidic electrolytes), and long-term stability in the presence of a hole scavenger. The presented method allows economical, facile growth of metal-free materials on different substrates without damaging the substrate-active layer interface and properties.

4. Experimental Section

Melem synthesis and preparation of supramolecular assemblies between melem (Mel) and melamine (M) were carried out according to the procedure of Xia et al.^[25]

Synthesis of Melem: 2,5,8-triamino-tri-s-triazine (melem) was synthesized by thermal condensation of melamine at 400 °C for 12 h in a ceramic crucible with a lid using a muffle furnace (under air), heated from room temperature to 400 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C min^{-1} . After the reaction, the oven was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature. The obtained bulk off-white powder was then ground into a fine powder using a mortar and pestle.

Preparation of Supramolecular Assemblies: Mel–M supramolecular assemblies with molar ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1 (denoted as MeIM, 2MeIM, and 3MeIM, respectively) were prepared by mixing suitable quantities of melamine and melem, with a total mass of $\approx 2 \text{ g}$ (both components combined), in 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tubes with 45 mL of deionized water. Then, the mixture was sonicated for 15 min, shaken in an orbital shaker (300 rpm, 24 h), and finally centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 5 min. The resulting solid phase (the Mel–M precipitate) was dried in a vacuum oven for 24 h. Lastly, the obtained bulk powder was ground into a fine powder using mortar and pestle for the next steps of the synthesis.

Preparation of Supramolecular Films (“Doctor-Blading”): Supramolecular films were prepared by mixing 0.50 g of MeIM, 2MeIM, or 3MeIM with 1.0 mL of ethylene glycol using a planetary centrifugal mixer ARV-310LED (Thinky mixer), using a single 10 mm zirconia ball at 1500 rpm for 5 min. The resulting paste was deposited on the FTO substrates using

the doctor-blade coating technique (a single layer of 3M Scotch Magic Tape 810 serving as the barrier to determine the paste height during deposition). Then, the films were dried on a heating plate in two steps: from room temperature at a heating ramp of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ until reaching $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, then increasing the temperature to the set point of $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min.

Synthesis of CN Films: Two FTO slides coated with the supramolecular films were wrapped with aluminum foil in a “sandwich”-like manner (as depicted in Scheme 1), with the films facing each other, in the presence of an additional 0.10 g melem powder between them. The “sandwiches” were inserted into a preheated nitrogen tube furnace (quartz tube with a 10 cm diameter) at $650\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $680\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, for 5, 10, or 20 min. The inlet side of the tube oven was connected to an incoming nitrogen flow to reduce oxygen presence, while the outlet side was kept open to allow easy access (to allow the introduction and removal of the “sandwiches” into the furnace). Then, the “sandwiches” were immediately taken out of the oven to cool down to room temperature naturally. Each “sandwich” was separated into two pieces (the two CN-coated FTO substrates) and excess CN powder (product of melem thermal polymerization) was removed gently using a scalpel, finally obtaining the CN films over FTO. The films are denoted as $\text{XMeM}_{T/t}$, where X is the molar ratio of melem to melamine in the supramolecular precursor, T is the calcination temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and t is the duration of the thermal process (min).

Additional experimental details are provided in the supporting information.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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A.T. performed most of the experiments, analyzed the data, and wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. S.M. assisted with PEC measurements and data analysis. V.R.B. helped with the synthetic procedure and graphics. G.M. performed XPS characterization. T.S. assisted with IPCE and oxygen production measurements. M.V. took part in analysis, elemental analysis measurements, SEM imaging, and manuscript review. M.S. supervised the study, cowrote and reviewed the paper, and acquired funding. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript. This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement no. 849 068). A.T. thanks KKL-JNF for financial support. The authors thank Roxana Golan for technical support with part of the SEM imaging, Keren Barchichat, Dr. Bar Elisha, and Dr. Orit Malka for technical support with elemental analysis measurements, and Rotem Geva for helping with data analysis.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

carbon nitride, fast heating, photoelectrochemical cells, water splitting

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Supporting Information

Minute-Scale High-Temperature Synthesis of Polymeric Carbon Nitride Photoanodes

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Michael Volokh, Menny Shalom**

Detailed synthetic procedures

Materials:

All reagents and solvents were used as received from their respective commercial vendors, without further purification: melamine (99%) and Na₂SO₄ (ACS reagent) from Sigma-Aldrich; triethanolamine (TEOA, 99%) from Glentham, UK; KOH (pellets, ≥85%, analytical grade) from Macron; NaOH 1 M aqueous solution from Loba-Chemie, India; NaH₂PO₄ (96%) and Na₂HPO₄ (98+%) from Alfa Aesar; sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, 96% w/w, AR grade) from Bio-Lab, Israel; acetone and ethanol (technical grade) from Romical, Israel.

Deionized water (18.2 MΩ cm resistivity at 25 °C, purified using a Millipore Direct-Q3 system) was used for all aqueous solutions preparation. Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO)-coated glass (12–14 Ω sq⁻¹) was purchased from Xop Glass company, Spain. Before use, the FTO was cut into rectangular pieces (1.3 cm × 2.5 cm) and sonicated with an aqueous detergent solution (Alconox, 1% m/v), ethanol, and acetone successively, for 15 min each, then dried in an air oven at 60 °C.

Synthesis of melem:

2,5,8-triamino-tri-*s*-triazine (melem) was synthesized by thermal condensation of melamine at 400 °C for 12 hours in a ceramic crucible with a lid using a muffle furnace (under air), heated from room temperature to 400 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. After the reaction, the oven was allowed to naturally cool down to room temperature. The obtained bulk off-white powder was then ground into fine powder using mortar and pestle.

Preparation of Melem–melamine supramolecular assemblies:

Melem–melamine (Mel–M) supramolecular assemblies with molar ratios of 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, and 4:1 (denoted as MelM, 2MelM, 3MelM, or 4MelM, respectively) were prepared by mixing suitable quantities of melamine and melem, with a total mass of ~2 g (both components), in 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tubes with 45 mL of DI water. Then, the mixture was sonicated for 15 min, shaken in an orbital shaker (300 rpm, 24 h), and finally centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 5 minutes. The resulting solid phase (the precipitate) was dried in a vacuum oven for 24 h. Lastly, the obtained bulk powder was ground into a fine powder using mortar and pestle for the next steps of the synthesis.

Preparation of supramolecular films ('doctor-blading'):

Supramolecular films were prepared by mixing 0.5 g of MelM, 2MelM, 3MelM, or 4MelM with 1 mL of ethylene glycol using a planetary centrifugal mixer ARV-310LED (Thinky mixer), using a single 10 mm zirconia ball at 1500 rpm for 5 minutes. The resulting paste was deposited on the FTO substrates using the doctor-blade coating technique (a single layer of 3M Scotch Magic Tape 810 serving as the

barrier to determine the paste height during deposition). Then, the films were dried on a heating plate in two steps: first, from room temperature at a heating ramp of 5 °C min⁻¹ until reaching 60 °C, then increasing the temperature to the set point of 85 °C for 30 min.

Synthesis of CN films:

Two FTO slides coated with the supramolecular films were wrapped with aluminum foil in a ‘sandwich’-like manner (as depicted in Scheme 1), with the films facing each other, in the presence of additional 0.10 g melem powder between them. The ‘sandwiches’ were inserted into a preheated nitrogen tube furnace (quartz tube with a 10 cm diameter) at 650 °C or 680 °C, for a duration of 5, 10, or 20 min. The inlet side of the tube oven was connected to an incoming nitrogen flow to reduce oxygen presence, while the outlet side was kept open to allow easy access (to allow the introduction and removal of the ‘sandwiches’ into the furnace). Then, the ‘sandwiches’ were immediately taken out of the oven to naturally cool down to room temperature. Each ‘sandwich’ was separated into two pieces (the two CN-coated FTO substrates) and excess CN powder (product of melem thermal polymerization) was removed, finally obtaining the CN films over FTO. The films are denoted as XMelM_{T/t}, where X is the molar ratio of melem to melamine in the supramolecular precursor, T is the calcination temperature (°C), and t is the duration of the thermal process (min).

Characterization:

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measurements were performed under nitrogen flow in a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹, in a 100 µL alumina crucible, using LABSYS evo by Setaram, France. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained using a PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer (equipped with an X'celerator position-sensitive detector) with a scanning time of ≈7 min for a 2θ range of 5°–60°, using Cu K_α radiation (λ = 1.54178 Å), operation parameters: 40 kV, 30 mA. Fourier-transform infrared

(FTIR) spectra were collected on a Thermo Scientific Nicolet iS5 using a diamond iD7 attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory. The chemical states of key elements were analyzed from X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements conducted on X-ray photoelectron spectrometer ESCALAB-Xi+ ultrahigh vacuum (4×10^{-10} bar) apparatus with an Al K_{α} X-ray source and a monochromator; all the binding energies in the XPS spectra were calibrated using the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV. XPS valence band spectra were also measured on this instrument, and the valence band values on the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) scale of the electrodes were calculated using the following formula (equation S1):

$$E_{\text{NHE}} (\text{V}) = \Phi + E_{\text{VB-XPS}} - 4.44 \quad (\text{S1})$$

where Φ is the work function of the instrument ($\Phi = 4.84$ eV), $E_{\text{VB-XPS}}$ is the measured valence band value, and 4.44 eV is the vacuum level. Elemental analysis of C, H, and N elements was obtained using a Thermo Scientific Flash Smart elemental analyzer OEA 2000; two tin crucibles of each material (2–3 mg) were measured for the quantification. The UV–vis diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS, measured as % R) were measured using a Cary 100 spectrophotometer equipped with a diffuse reflectance accessory (DRA). To determine the absorbance spectra of the films a Kubelka-Munk function, $F(R)$, was calculated. The optical band gap (E_{g}) was determined using Tauc plot analysis, assuming a direct band gap. Photoluminescence (PL) spectra were collected on a Horiba Scientific FluroMax 4 fluorimeter, with an excitation wavelength of $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 380$ nm. The morphology of the samples was characterized using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI VERIOS 460L) operated at 3.0 kV, 25 pA, using an Everhart–Thornley secondary electron detector; the samples were sputtered with 12 nm gold before analysis to avoid charging.

Photoelectrochemical measurements:

All photoelectrochemical measurements were performed using a standard three-electrode configuration with a Pt plate (1.0 cm²) as the counter electrode, Ag/AgCl (saturated KCl) as the reference electrode, and the synthesized CN films over FTO substrates as the working electrodes. The electrolyte was either (i) alkaline—0.1 M KOH aqueous solution (pH 13.04), (ii) neutral—phosphate buffer (pH 6.67, prepared by dissolving 1.15 g of NaH₂PO₄ and 1.88 g of Na₂HPO₄ in 500 mL H₂O), or (iii) acidic—0.5 M sulfuric acid (pH 0.46). When mentioned, 10% v/v triethanolamine (TEOA) was added to the alkaline electrolyte (0.1 M KOH) as a hole scavenger. All potential values versus (vs) Ag/AgCl were converted to values vs the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) using the Nernst equation at room temperature:

$$V_{\text{RHE}} = V_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.059 \times \text{pH} + 0.197 \text{ (V)} \quad (\text{S2})$$

The potentiostats for chronoamperometry, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), and EIS measurements were PalmSens 3 or EMstat 4SHR (PalmSens, Netherlands) running the latest PStace 5 for windows software. Photocurrent density was measured at a bias potential of 1.23 V vs RHE under 1-sun illumination (power density of ~100 mW cm⁻²) supplied by a solar simulator (Newport 300 W Xe arc lamp, equipped with an AM 1.5G and water filters, calibrated using a Newport 919P power meter). Illumination into the cell through a flat quartz window in either front- or back-side illumination of the tested photoanode. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were performed in the dark and under 1-sun illumination in the range of 0–1.8 V vs RHE at a scan rate of 0.02 V s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was recorded at applied potentials of 1.23 V vs RHE in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution. Incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) measurements were collected using Zahner CIMPS-QE/IPCE photoelectrochemical workstation coupled with a TLS03 tunable light source controlled by a PP211 potentiostat (Zahner-Elektrik, Germany) in a dedicated three-electrode photoelectrochemical cell (PEEC-2); Ag/AgCl (sat. KCl) was used as the reference electrode

and Pt coil as the counter electrode. The electrolyte was an alkaline aqueous solution of 0.1 M KOH with or without addition of 10% v/v TEOA. The IPCE values were calculated using Equation S3, where J is the photocurrent density, λ is the illumination wavelength, I is the incident illumination energy flux (calibrated to an illumination spot of 8 mm in diameter), and 1240 is the units conversion factor. The calculation was performed by the coupled ThalesXT software.

$$\text{IPCE (\%)} = \frac{J(\text{A cm}^{-2}) \cdot 1240}{\lambda(\text{nm}) \cdot I(\text{W cm}^{-2})} \times 100 \% \quad (\text{S3})$$

The hole extraction efficiency (η) of the material was calculated using Equation S4:

$$\eta(\%) = \frac{J_{\text{KOH}}}{J_{\text{TEOA}}} \times 100\% \quad (\text{S4})$$

where J_{KOH} is the current density measured in 0.1 M KOH, J_{TEOA} is the current density measured in 0.1 M KOH containing 10% v/v TEOA, assuming that all photogenerated holes are consumed in the presence of the hole scavenger.

Oxygen evolution quantification was performed utilizing a TROXROB10 fiber-optic oxygen sensor, connected to a FireSting-O₂ meter (Pyroscience, Germany). The chronoamperometry measurement was conducted in a two-compartment cell, with the working and reference electrodes in one cell, and the counter electrode in the other, at 1.23 V vs RHE under 1-sun illumination in 0.1 M KOH. The system was purged with 99.999% N₂(g) until reaching 0% oxygen, with a background measurement (serving as the baseline) subtracted from the results. The Faradaic efficiency (FE) was calculated using Equation (S5):

$$\text{FE(\%)} = \frac{\text{experimental amount of gas } (\mu\text{mol})}{\text{theoretical amount of gas } (\mu\text{mol})} \times 100\% \quad (\text{S5})$$

The theoretical amount of gas was calculated using Equation S6 from the measured current:

$$n = \frac{I \times t}{z \times F} \quad (\text{S6})$$

where n is the theoretical amount of hydrogen (mol), I is the current (A), t is the time (s), z is the number of electrons in the reaction (4 for oxygen), and F is the Faraday constant (96485 C mol^{-1}).

Hydrogen evolution quantification was measured at regular intervals of 5 min and analyzed by gas chromatography (Agilent 7820 GC system). Before measurement, nitrogen was purged for 45 min. Faradaic efficiency was calculated using equation S5, while the theoretical amount of gas was calculated using equation S6.

Supporting Information Figures and Tables

Table S1. Comparison of MeIM680/10 activity as a photoanode with previously reported CN-based photoanodes under different conditions.

Supramolecular assembly or monomer used for synthesis; ^a reaction conditions	CN-based photoanode (abbreviated name)	Electrolyte	Photocurrent density at 1.23 V vs RHE	Illumination	Reference
3:1 Melem-M + melem powder Calcination - 10 mins at 680 °C, preheated tube oven with constant nitrogen flow, cooling down at room temperature.	3MeIM _{680/10}	0.1 M KOH	120 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$	1-sun illumination (power density of $\sim 100 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$) supplied by a solar simulator (Newport 300 W Xe arc lamp, equipped with an AM 1.5G and water filters, calibrated using a Newport 919P power meter)	This work
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	190 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$		
		phosphate buffer	200 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$		
		0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	200 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$		
3:1 Melem-M + melem powder Calcination - of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂ with 120 mL min ⁻¹ flow rate	3MeIM _{550/4 h}	0.1 M KOH	30 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$	1-sun illumination (power density of $\sim 100 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$) supplied by a solar simulator (Newport 300 W Xe arc lamp, equipped with an AM 1.5G and water filters, calibrated using a Newport 919P power meter)	This work
Melamine-HCl supramolecular assembly; hydrothermal treatment; + M vapor. Calcination – tube furnace, heating rate of 5 min ⁻¹ to 530 °C for 4 h heating under a constant N ₂ flow.	CN _{M-HCl(HT)}	0.1 M KOH	95 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[1]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	310 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$		

Cyanuric acid, M, and KCl; solvothermal treatment in methanol; + M Vapor Calcination – tube furnace, heating rate of 5 min ⁻¹ to 520 °C for 2 h heating under a constant N ₂ flow.	CN-CMK-s-MeOH	0.1 M KOH	0.14 ± 0.01 mA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[2]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	0.30 ± 0.01 mA cm ⁻²		
NaBH ₄ + thiourea; + M vapor Calcination – tube furnace, heating rate of 5 min ⁻¹ to 500 °C for 2 h heating under a constant N ₂ flow.	CN _{TUB}	0.1 M KOH	870 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[3]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	1500 μA cm ⁻²		
Thiourea; + M vapor Calcination – tube furnace, heating rate of 5 min ⁻¹ to 500 °C for 2 h heating under a constant N ₂ flow.	CN _{TU}	0.1 M KOH	160 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[3]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	260 μA cm ⁻²		
M, thiourea; + M vapor Calcination – tube furnace, heating rate of 5 min ⁻¹ to 500 °C for 2 h heating under a constant N ₂ flow.	CN _{TM}	0.1 M KOH	353 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[4]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	565 μA cm ⁻²		
		0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	305 μA cm ⁻²		
Melem and M; + M vapor Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂ with 120 mL min ⁻¹ flow rate	CN-MeM/M _{0.20}	0.1 M KOH	133 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[5]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	383 μA cm ⁻²		
Cyanuric acid, M, tetracyanoethylene	CN-CMT ₂	0.1 M KOH	60 μA cm ⁻²		[6]

Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	160 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	
Cyanuric acid, M; + M vapor Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂	CN-CM ₁₂₀ M	0.1 M KOH	47 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[7]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	122 μA cm ⁻²		
Urea; + M vapor Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂	CN-U ₁₀ M _{0.5}	0.1 M KOH	110 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[8]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	300 μA cm ⁻²		
M, melem; + M vapor Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂	CNM+mlm	0.1 M KOH	160 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[9]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	380 μA cm ⁻²		
M Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂	Porous crystalline CN film	0.1 M KOH	116 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[10]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	245 μA cm ⁻²		
M and KSCN Calcination – 500 °C for 4 h at a ramping rate of 2.3 °C min ⁻¹ in a tubular furnace under nitrogen	K-PHI	1.0 M NaOH	800 μA cm ⁻²	Solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[11]
M and graphene oxide (GO) Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂	CN-MR with reduced graphene oxide (rGO)	0.1 M KOH	241 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[12]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	563 μA cm ⁻²		
M, GO; in situ formed NiFeO _x H _y oxidation cocatalyst	CN-MR/ NiFeO _x H _y	0.1 M KOH	472 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[12]

Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under N ₂		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	598 μA cm ⁻²		
M and trithiocyanuric acid Calcination- 550 °C for 2 h using a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹	PCN films	0.1 M KOH	650 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , AM 1.5G	[13]
M, cyanuric acid, GO Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h under nitrogen flow	CN/rGO	0.1 M KOH	72 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[14]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	660 μA cm ⁻²		
M and cyanuric chloride Calcination - 450 °C for 3 h at a heating rate of 5 °C min ⁻¹ under an Ar flow (60 mL min ⁻¹) in a tubular furnace	Compact carbon nitride polymer	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	230 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[15]
M, GO Calcination- 550 °C for 4 h under nitrogen flow	In situ grown porous CN/rGO (embedded rGO)	0.1 M KOH	124.5 μA cm ⁻²	Xe-based solar simulator, 100 mW cm ⁻² , AM1.5G	[16]
		0.1 M KOH + 10% TEOA	272 μA cm ⁻²		
Cobalt chloride hexahydrate, M, and thiourea Calcination - 500 °C for 4 h, heating rate of 2.3 °C min ⁻¹ under a nitrogen flow	2CSCN	1.0 M NaOH	200 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[17]
M and 2,6- diamino pyridine Calcination - 3 h at 600 °C with heating rate of 3 °C min ⁻¹	CMD5 (modified CN)	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ containing 0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₃ and 0.01 M Na ₂ S	100 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[18]
Dicyandiamide and boric acid Calcination -	s-BCN	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	103 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[19]

20 mins at 600 °C					
Cyanuric acid and 2,4-diamino-6-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine Calcination - 500 °C for 4 h under nitrogen with a heating rate of 2.3 °C min ⁻¹	S-doped thin films of phenyl-modified CN	0.1 M KOH	60 μA cm ⁻²	50 W white LED (λ > 410 nm, HLN-60H-24A, Mean Well)	[20]
M and trithiocyanuric acid Calcination - 500 °C for 4 h with a ramping rate of 3 °C min ⁻¹ under a constant nitrogen flow (100 cm ³ /min)	PCN	1 M KOH	100 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[21]
M Calcination - 600 °C for 3 h with a ramping rate of 3 °C min ⁻¹	g-CN400	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄	75 μA cm ⁻²	100 mW cm ⁻² , 1.5 AM	[22]
Cyanuric chloride and cyanuric acid; over titania Calcination - 450 °C under an Ar flow	CNBC-U/TiO ₂	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	32 μA cm ⁻²	1-sun solar simulator, 1.5 AM	[23]
Melem, carbon black. laser-derived CN + surface modification by M	M-LCN	0.1 M NaOH	73.12	AM 1.5 G illumination (100 mW cm ⁻²) using a PLS-SXE300 light source	[24]
		10% (v/v) TEOA in 0.1 M NaOH	146.70		
Thiourea, DCDA. Calcination – N ₂ with flow rate of 50 mL min ⁻¹ , heated at 300°C for 1 h and subsequently 500°C for 6 h, with a heating rate of 3°C min ⁻¹ .	CNDT _{0.013}	140	0.1M NaOH	100 mW cm ⁻² AM 1.5G	[25]
		170	10% (v/v) TEOA in 0.1 M NaOH		
		383 μA cm ⁻²	10% (v/v) TEOA in 0.1 M KOH		

^aM, GO, and rGO stand for melamine, graphene oxide, and reduced graphene oxide, respectively.

Figure S1. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of melam, melamine, MeIM, 2MeIM, and 3MeIM, showing improved thermal stability in samples with higher melam content. The remaining mass percent of melamine, MeIM, 2MeIM, 3MeIM and melam at 650 °C is 2.4%, 50.9%, 56.7%, 63.8% and 77.5%, respectively. The remaining mass percent of melamine, MeIM, 2MeIM, 3MeIM and melam at 680 °C is 1.72%, 39.1%, 43.9%, 50.8% and 63.9%, respectively. The heating rate in the measurement is 5 °C min⁻¹.

Figure S2. Cross-sectional SEM image of a typical 3MeIM film.

	C (at. %)	N (at. %)	H (at. %)	O (at. %)	C/N ratio
3MeIM _{650/10}	26.26	31.98	30.77	10.99	0.821
3MeIM _{650/20}	27.59	32.76	29.03	10.62	0.842
3MeIM _{680/5}	26.24	31.06	33.94	8.76	0.845
3MeIM _{680/10}	27.89	32.72	29.35	10.04	0.852
3MeIM _{680/20}	28.06	32.46	28.74	10.74	0.864

Figure S3. Crack formation and partial peeling-off of a 4MeIM film during the preparation process.

Table S2. Elemental analysis of the films. The percentage of O in the table was obtained by subtracting the directly measured C, N, and H values from 100%.

Figure S4. UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra, presented as the Kubelka-Munk function, $F(R)$, of 3MeIM_{650/10}, 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/5}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20}.

Figure S5. Digital photos of 3MeIM films over FTO substrates, showing that 3MeIM_{650/10} and 3MeIM_{680/5} have a pale yellowish shade, while 3MeIM_{680/20} exhibits a stronger yellow color—typical to CN materials. 3MeIM_{650/20} and 3MeIM_{680/10} display an intermediate yellowish shade.

Figure S6. XPS spectra for valence band determination for a) 3MeIM_{650/10}, b) 3MeIM_{650/20}, c) 3MeIM_{680/5}, d) 3MeIM_{680/10}, and e) 3MeIM_{680/20}. The determined values (2.01–2.33 eV vs NHE) are indicated in the legend of each panel.

Figure S7. (a, b) Top-view SEM images of 3MeIM_{680/10} at high magnification.

Figure S8. a) Two 40.8 cm² (6.8 cm × 6.0 cm) 3MeIM_{680/10} films, prepared in the same 'sandwich'. b) 50.0 cm² (10.0 cm × 5.0 cm) 3MeIM_{680/20} film.

Figure S9. Full adhesion test procedure for a 3MeIM_{680/10} electrode.

Figure S10. Chronoamperometry measurements of MeIM_{680/10}, 2MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/10} (photocurrent density at 1.23 V vs RHE) in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under cycling (on/off) back-side 1-sun illumination.

Figure S11. Chronoamperometry measurements of a) $3\text{MeIM}_{650/20}$, b) $\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, and c) $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$ (photocurrent density at 1.23 V vs RHE) in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution under cycling (on/off) front-side (plotted with red curves) and back-side (plotted with black curves) 1-sun illumination. The front-side measurement of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$ lasted 5 min instead of 10 min as all the other measurements.

Figure S12. Stability test of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ in the presence of a hole scavenger, measuring the current density under applied bias voltage of 1.23 V vs RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution containing 10% v/v TEOA for 20 hours of continuous 1-sun back-side illumination.

Figure S13. Three different front- and back-side chronoamperometry measurements of 3MeIM_{680/10} under applied bias voltage of 1.23 V vs RHE in 0.1 M KOH aqueous solution containing 10% v/v TEOA.

Figure S14. Calculated charge transfer efficiency of $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$ as a function applied potential; assuming 100% charge extraction in the presence of the hole scavenger (10% v/v TEOA in 0.1 M KOH), under a continuous 1-sun back-side illumination.

Figure S15. Chronoamperometry measurements of $3\text{MeIM}_{650/20}$, $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, and $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$ in a) acidic environment 0.5 M H_2SO_4 (aq) (pH 0.46) and b) neutral phosphate buffer (pH 6.67) under cyclic back-side 1-sun illumination at 1.23 V vs RHE.

Figure S16. Stability (1 h chronoamperometry) measurements of 3MeIM_{680/10} in basic 0.1 M KOH(aq) (pH 13, black curve), neutral phosphate buffer (pH 7, red curve) and acidic 0.5 M H₂SO₄(aq) (pH 0.46, green curve) under continuous back-side 1-sun illumination at 1.23 V vs RHE.

Table S3. Composition of 3MeIM_{680/10} before and after 30-min chronoamperometry measurement at 1.23 V vs RHE in 0.1 M KOH, as obtained from XPS spectral deconvolution and analysis.

	Before measurement (at. %)	After measurement (at. %)
C 1s	44.69	44.70
N 1s	54.23	49.76
O 1s	1.08	5.54

Figure S17. Control chronoamperometry experiments measured with three different types of CN electrodes. a) 3MeIM_{550/240} (3MeIM ‘sandwich’ calcined at 550 °C for 240 min, i.e., 4 h, a common procedure for CN film synthesis). b) 3MeIM_{650/20}, 3MeIM_{680/10}, and 3MeIM_{680/20}, calcined without melem powder between the two supramolecular films (the ‘sandwich’). c) 3MeIM_{680/10} 2L (3MeIM_{680/10} that was prepared with two layers of scotch tape in the doctor blade procedure of the precursor deposition on FTO). All measurements were performed in 0.1 M KOH(aq) under 1-sun illumination at 1.23 vs RHE.

Figure S18. Cracking and partial peeling off of 3MeIM films over FTO that were prepared with 2 layers of scotch tape, compared to 1-layer 3MeIM films.

Figure S19. PL spectra of the reference CN films compared to $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$; $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 380 \text{ nm}$.

Figure S20. Nyquist plot analysis (fitted model) of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements of $3\text{MeIM}_{650/20}$, $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10}$, and $3\text{MeIM}_{680/20}$, $3\text{MeIM}_{550/4 \text{ h}}$, $3\text{MeIM}_{680/10} \text{ 2L}$ and

3MeIM_{680/10} without melem powder at 1.23 V vs RHE in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄(aq). Inset: the equivalent circle used for fitting.

Figure S21. a) Oxygen evolution reaction quantification using 3MeIM_{680/10} photoanode in 0.1 M KOH at 1.23 V vs RHE under constant back-side 1-sun illumination (red curve), compared to the theoretical values of production (black curve), calculated from b) The chronoamperometric measurement of 3MeIM_{680/10}, recorded during the gas production measurement. The corresponding Faradaic efficiency value is 35.6% after 33 minutes of measurement.

Figure S22. Hydrogen production quantification using 3MeIM_{680/10} photoanode and a Pt counter electrode in a PEC water-splitting sealed cell using 0.1 M KOH electrolyte at 1.23 V vs. RHE under constant back-side 1-sun illumination.

Figure S23. SEM images of 3MeI_{M680/10} electrode following a stability test of 20 h (post-PEC), shown

in Figure 4c. a) Cross-sectional image, and b,c) Top-view.

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